

Notes on the *Helix gaudryi* (A. d'Orbigny, 1839) complex (Gastropoda, Stylommatophora: Helicidae) from the Canary Islands

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INTRODUCTION

The nominal species *Helix gaudryi* was originally described in 1839 and first figured in 1842 (pl. 1 fig. 4) by A. d'Orbigny in his contribution to the malacofauna of the Canary Islands in volume 2, part 2 of Webb & Berthelot's "Histoire naturelle des Iles Canaries" (1836-1842). He mentioned "envoyée de l'île de Gomera" as the type locality of the taxon. Later, Mousson (1872: 97) and Wollaston (1878: 356-357) doubted that *H. gaudryi* actually originated from La Gomera. Both Mousson and Wollaston considered similarly shaped specimens from Gran Canaria to represent the species. Mousson (1872) mentioned the species from Gran Canaria, more precisely from the locality "El Monte de San-Martao" [= Vega de San Mateo], where it was collected by K. von Fritsch (Fig. 8). Wollaston (1878) mentioned as locality "El Monte (particularly about Los Laurealos, and within the great crater of the Bandama mountain)". Both collecting sites are located geographically close to Tafira Alta in the north-eastern part of Gran Canaria. Shells from these localities, however, have a distinctly malleated surface sculpture (Fig. 18), whereas the original description by A. d'Orbigny does not mention any malleation. Therefore, we here consider the name *gaudryi* as having been wrongly applied to populations of a species from the north-eastern part of Gran Canaria. That the current usage of the name is indeed incorrect is corroborated by the examination of the syntypes of *Helix gaudryi*, which are preserved in the collection of the Natural History Museum (London) (Fig. 2). As a consequence of the more recently erroneous application of the name *gaudryi*, e.g., by Bank et al. (2002), Verbinnen & Swinnen (2014) described *Hemicycla idairae* (Fig. 1) as a new species from La Gomera, which is in our opinion identical to d'Orbigny's *Helix gaudryi* based on general shell shape and sculpture, as well as colouration (Fig. 3).

Keywords: *Hemicycla*, La Gomera, Gran Canaria, new synonym, new combination, Gastropoda, Helicidae

The complex nomenclatorial situation around the nominate taxon *Helix gaudryi* A. d'Orbigny, 1839, caused by a mix-up of the occurrence of similar looking species from La Gomera and Gran Canaria, is clarified. The type locality La Gomera for *Hemicycla gaudryi* (d'Orbigny, 1839) is confirmed, and a lectotype is selected. As a consequence, the recently described *Hemicycla idairae* Verbinnen & Swinnen, 2014 from La Gomera is synonymized (syn. nov.). The earliest available name for the *Hemicycla* species from Gran Canaria is *Helix ripochi* J. Mabille, 1882. A number of taxa of Mabille described in 1883 from Gran Canaria are synonymized with *Hemicycla ripochi*: *Helix amblasmodon*, *H. janthina*, *H. themera*, *H. zorgia* (all syn. nov.). The Quaternary fossil *Helix ledruui* J. Mabille, 1883, formerly thought to belong to this complex, is synonymized with the subspecies *Hemicycla psathyra bituminosa* (J. Mabille, 1883) (syn. nov.). For the taxa *Helix bituminosa* and *H. ripochi* of Mabille, lectotypes are designated and figured.

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Margry, Swinnen & Artiles Ruiz (2024: 76), when describing their *Hemicycla nisamarae*, correctly stated in their introduction that *Helix gaudryi* is probably an older name for *Hemicycla idairae* Verbinnen & Swinnen, 2014, which therefore should be used for the taxon. The fact that *Helix gaudryi* is actually a species from La Gomera and not from Gran Canaria was already pointed out by Groh (2013), who used – following a hint by Marco T. Neiber – tentatively the name *Hemicycla* cf. *themera* (Mabille, 1883) for the species from Gran Canaria. In an earlier assessment for the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN), Groh (2011) also incorrectly used the name *gaudryi* for the species from Gran Canaria. Langerhaert & Brosens (2020: 5) also applied the name *gaudryi* to the species from Gran Canaria, but these authors also stated that the correct species epithet may rather be Mabille's name *themera*.

A recent discussion with the authorities of MolluscaBase and the Species Information Service (SIS) of the IUCN led to the demand to explain the synonymization of the nominal species *Helix gaudryi* and *Hemicycla idairae* in detail. This resulted in the following notes on the name *Helix gaudryi* d'Orbigny, 1839 and its synonymy. We also take into consideration the nominal taxa previously considered to be synonyms of that name, which were used for specimens from the island of Gran Canaria by Bank, Groh & Ripken (2002: 131), namely *Helix janthina* J. Mabille, 1883; *H. ledrui* J. Mabille, 1883; *H. ripochi* J. Mabille, 1882; *H. themera* J. Mabille, 1883; *H. zorgia* J. Mabille, 1883 and possibly also *H. amblasmodon* J. Mabille, 1883. Since some of these nominal taxa refer to yet another taxon from Gran Canaria, the nominal species *Helix bituminosa* J. Mabille, 1883 is also discussed in this paper.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The work is based on the evaluation of the original literature and a visual and morphometric comparison of the preserved type material corresponding to the taxa described and discussed by d'Orbigny (1836-1842), Lowe (1861), Mabille (1882, 1883a, b, 1885a, b) and Verbinnen & Swinnen (2014).

Abbreviations: IUCN = International Union for Conservation of Nature; KBIN = Koninklijk Belgisch Instituut voor Natuurwetenschappen, Brussels, Belgium; NHMUK = The Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom; MNHN = Muséum national d'Histoire naturelle, Paris, France; SIS = Species Information Service; ZMZ = Zoological Museum Zurich, Switzerland.

SYSTEMATIC PART

Superfamily Helicoidea Rafinesque, 1815

Family Helicidae Rafinesque, 1815

Subfamily Helicinae Rafinesque, 1815

Tribe Allognathini Westerlund, 1903

Genus *Hemicycla* Swainson, 1840

Hemicycla Swainson, 1840: 164. Type species (by monotypy): *Helix plicaria* Lamarck, 1816.

Hemicycla gaudryi (A. d'Orbigny, 1839)

(Figs 1-7)

Helix gaudryi A. d'Orbigny, 1839: 57-58. Type locality: «envoyée de l'île de Gomera». Lectotype (here designated) (Fig. 2) + 2 paralectotypes NHMUK.1854.9.28.41.

Helix gaudryi — d'Orbigny, 1842: pl. 3 figs 15-17 (here reproduced Fig. 4).

Helix gaudryi — Pfeiffer, 1859: 231 (only the reference to d'Orbigny and Poey).

Helix gaudryi var.? — Mousson, 1872: pl. 5 figs 18-19 (here reproduced Fig. 7A).

Helix gaudryi Orbigny? (Pfeiffer 1859) – Pfeiffer, 1872: pl. 124 figs 18-19 (here reproduced Fig. 7B); 1874: 98.

Hemicycla idairae Verbinnen & Swinnen, 2014: 72-76, figs. 1-3, fig. 2 (animal), pls 1-2 (shell + habitat). Type locality: “Area of Antoncojo, Playa Santiago near La Gomera Airport; occurring at an altitude of 50 to 400 metres above sea level”. Holotype KBIN, IG:32688/MT.3048 (Fig. 1A).

Hemicycla idairae & *H. gaudryi* — Margry, Swinnen & Artiles Ruiz, 2024: 76.

Hemicycla gaudryi (in map only partim) — Neiber & Groh, 2025 SIS IUCN: <https://www.iucnredlist.org/species/253471618/253472067>

The conspecificity of the nominal taxa *Helix gaudryi* and *Hemicycla idairae* is clearly evident, in our opinion, because of the very close resemblance of the type material of both taxa, i.e., a specimen of *Helix gaudryi* in the d'Orbigny-collection (NHMUK.1854.9.28.41, herewith designated as the lectotype) with the holotype of *Hemicycla idairae* (KBIN IG:32688/MT.3048). We therefore consider the latter name as a subjective junior synonym of the former. The distribution of the species on the island of La Gomera is circumscribed by Neiber & Groh (2025) (Fig. 5). See Fig. 6 for a photo of a living specimen.

The figures of Mousson (1872: pl. 5, figs 16-17; Pfeiffer, 1872: pl. 124 figs 16-17) (Fig. 7A), which are identical except for Pfeiffer's figures being coloured (Fig. 7B), do not correspond to the species from La Gomera. Indeed, the figured shell seemed either to originate from “Gran Canaria” (ex coll. Fritsch) or from Gran Canaria, “El Monte de San-Marta” (ex coll. Wollaston). The shell shows in these figures a weak yet distinct ribbing but no malleation. The specimen

Figs 1-4. *Hemicycla gaudryi* (A. d'Orbigny, 1839). **1A.** Holotype *Hemicycla idairae* Verbinnen & Swinnen, 2014, Antoncojo, Playa Santiago, La Gomera. Dorsal and ventral view (KBIN, IG:32688/MT.3048), after Verbinnen & Swinnen (2014: pl. 1, figs 1, 1a), width 17.0 mm (photograph Gilbert Verbinnen). **1B.** Topotype *Hemicycla idairae*, frontal view (coll. Groh CKG-03030) width 17.4 mm (photograph Klaus Groh). **2.** Lectotype (herewith designated) of *Helix gaudryi* A. d'Orbigny, 1839, La Gomera, (NHMUK.1854.9.28.41) (photograph Jon Ablett). **3.** Paratype *Hemicycla idairae* Verbinnen & Swinnen, 2014, coll. Frank Swinnen, from the type locality, after Verbinnen & Swinnen (2014: pl. 2, fig. 6) (photograph Gilbert Verbinnen). **4.** *Helix gaudryi* A. d'Orbigny, 1839, modified from d'Orbigny (1842: pl. 3, figs. 17, 15, 16). Scale bar: 5 mm for Figs 1-3, Fig. 4 not scaled.

Fig. 5. Map of La Gomera denoting the distribution of *Hemicycla gaudryi* (A. d'Orbigny, 1839) from Species Information Service (IUCN) after Neiber & Groh, 2025. Black dot: type locality of *H. idairae* Verbinnen & Swinnen, 2014.

Fig. 6. *Hemicycla gaudryi* (A. d’Orbigny, 1839), live specimen from La Gomera, N of airport at Playa Santiago, 5-x.2022 (photograph Ingrid Margry-Moonen).

Fig. 7. *Hemicycla gaudryi* (A. d’Orbigny, 1839). **7A:** Reproduction of the illustration from Mousson (1872: pl. 5 figs. 18-19 – as *Helix gaudryi* var.); **7B:** Reproduction of the illustration from Pfeiffer (1872: pl. 124 figs 18-19 – as *Helix gaudryi* Orbigny? (Pfeiffer, 1859). Not scaled.

figured from the Wollaston-collection could be found in the Mousson-collection (ZMZ 507680; Fig. 8B) and is identical to the *Hemicycla*-species from the north-eastern part of Gran Canaria, up till now called *Hemicycla gaudryi* auct. (non d’Orbigny, 1839) [= *Hemicycla ripochi*]. The distinct radial riblets on the surface of the shell are exaggerated in the figures of Mousson and Pfeiffer.

***Hemicycla ripochi* (J. Mabilie, 1882) comb. nov.**
(Figs 8-20)

Helix gaudryi — Pfeiffer, 1859: 231 (without the reference to d’Orbigny and to Poey) [non *Helix gaudryi* A. d’Orbigny, 1839].

Helix gaudryi d’Orb. – Mousson, 1872: 97-98 (not from La Gomera), pl. 5 figs 16-17 (figs in b/w as shown in colour in Fig. 8A, original specimen to figs = Fig. 8B).

Helix gaudryi Orbigny? (Mouss.) – Pfeiffer, 1872: pl. 124 figs 16-17 (here reproduced Fig. 8A); 1874: 97-98.

Helix gaudryi — Wollaston, 1878: 356-357 [non *Helix gaudryi* d’Orbigny, 1839].

Helix ripochi J. Mabilie, 1882: 142-143. Type locality:

Fig. 8. *Hemicycla ripochi* (J. Mabille, 1882). **8A.** Reproduction of the illustration from Pfeiffer (1872: pl. 124 figs 16-17 – as *Helix gaudryi* Orbigny? (Mouss.), identical with the b/w illustration from Mousson (1872: pl. 5 figs 16-17 – as *Helix gaudryi*). **8B.** Photographs of the shell figured in 8A preserved in the Mousson-collection (ZMZ 507680) from Gran Canaria, El Monte S Martão, ex Wollaston, 1870, width 24.8 mm (photograph Eike Neubert).

Fig. 9. *Hemicycla ripochi* (J. Mabille, 1882). Mentioned as *Hemicycla gaudryi* (d'Orbigny, 1839). Gran Canaria [without precise locality data] on the website of Flickr, width 23.8 mm (photograph C. & A. Evanno) (https://www.flickr.com/photos/landshells_freshwater_gastropods/39141678421/).

«Grande-Canarie» (ex coll. Ripoché) (more exactly: «La Grande Canarie: à Lomo de Capan» – see Mabille, 1885b: 41) [= Lomo de Capón near Tafira Alta [ca 28°03'45"N - 15°28'56"W]. Type material: syntypes MNHN IM-2000-29137/8 (Fig. 17, lectotype herewith designated).

Helix janthina J. Mabille, 1883b: 120-121. Type locality: „In magna Canaria a Dom.[inum] H.[enri-René Le Tourneux] de la Perraudière et [Miguel & Michel] Ripoché lecta” [probably in or near Las Palmas de Gran Canaria]. Type

material: holotype MNHN IM-2000-39874/1 (Fig. 18). **Syn. nov.** Junior homonym of *Helix janthina* Linnaeus, 1758 (= *Janthina janthina*; Epitoniidae).

Helix amblasmodon J. Mabille, 1883b: 123-124. Type locality: “In Magna Canaria prope Agaete” (ex coll. Ripoché) [most probably erroneous, as the taxon corresponds very well to *H. ripochi*; note that Ripoché lived near Las Palmas de Gran Canaria]. Type material: holotype MNHN IM-2000-28688/1 (Fig. 20). **Syn. nov.**

Fig. 10. Map of NE Gran Canaria denoting the distribution of *Hemicycla ripochi* (J. Mabille, 1882) from Species Information Service (iucn) after Neiber & Groh, 2025. Black dot: type locality of *H. ripochi*.

Fig. 11. *Hemicycla ripochi*, live specimen from Gran Canaria (photograph Frank Walther).

Figs 12-16. *Hemicycla ripochi* (J. Mabille, 1882). **12.** *Helix janthina* J. Mabille, 1883, fig. reproduced from Mabille (1885: pl. 16 fig. 10). **13.** *Helix ripochi* J. Mabille, 1882, figs. reproduced from Mabille (1885: pl. 17, fig. 2). **14.** *Helix themera* J. Mabille, 1883, fig. reproduced from Mabille (1885: pl. 15 fig. 11). **15.** *Helix zorgia* J. Mabille, 1883, fig. reproduced from Mabille (1885: pl. 16 fig. 12). **16.** *Helix amblasmodon* J. Mabille, 1883, fig. reproduced from Mabille (1885: pl. 15 fig. 2).

Figs 17-20. *Hemicycla ripochi* (J. Mabille, 1882). **17.** *Helix ripochi* J. Mabille, 1882, lectotype (here designated) MNHN IM-2000-29137, width 25.2 mm. Type locality: «La Grande Canarie: à Lomo de Capan». **18.** *Helix janthina* J. Mabille, 1883, holotype MNHN IM-2000-39874, width 27.1 mm. Type locality: „In magna Canaria a Dom.[inum] H.[enri-René Le Tourneux] de la Perraudière et [Miguel & Michel] Ripoché lecta”. **19.** *Helix zorgia* J. Mabille, 1883, holotype MNHN IM-2000-29079, width 24.4 mm. Type locality: “In Magna Canaria”. **20.** *Helix amblasmodon* J. Mabille, 1883, holotype MNHN IM-2000-28688, width 28.8 mm. Type locality: “In Magna Canaria prope Agaete” [probably erroneous]. Photographs: Priscillia Gaël Bourguignon (MNHN).

Helix themera J. Mabille, 1883b: 126. Type locality: “In insula Madera” (ex coll. Bourguignat) [according to Mabille, 1885b: 40 the type locality is “La Grande Canarie; au Barranco Angostura” (ex coll. Tarnier)] [ca 28°02'49"N - 15°29'12"W]. Type material: syntypes not found in MNHN. **Syn. nov.**

Helix zorgia J. Mabille, 1883b: 127. Type locality: “In Magna Canaria” (ex coll. Ripoché). Type material: holotype MNHN IM-2000-29079/1 (Fig. 17). **Syn. nov.**

Helix amblasmodon — Mabille, 1885a: pl. 15 fig. 2 (here reproduced Fig. 16); 1885b: 46-47.

Helix themera — Mabille, 1885a: pl. 15 fig. 11 (here reproduced Fig. 14); 1885b: 39-40.

Helix janthina — Mabille, 1885a: pl. 16 fig. 10 (here reproduced Fig. 12); 1885b: 42-43.

Helix zorgia — Mabille, 1885a: pl. 16 fig. 12 (here reproduced Fig. 15); 1885b: 47-48.

Helix ripochi — Mabille, 1885a: pl. 17 fig. 2 (here reproduced Fig. 13); 1885b: 40-42.

Hemicycla gaudryi — Bank, Groh & Ripken, 2002: 131 (without the synonym *ledrui*).

Hemicycla cf. *themera* — Groh, 2011: SIS IUCN: <https://www.iucnredlist.org/species/156410/4940891>

Hemicycla gaudryi — Langerhaert & Brosens, 2020: 5.

Hemicycla gaudryi (only in the map partim) — Neiber & Groh, 2025 SIS IUCN: <https://www.iucnredlist.org/species/253471618/253472067>

Because the nominal species *Helix gaudryi* originates from the island of La Gomera and because the *Hemicycla* population from the north-eastern part of Gran Canaria does not match the character states reported for *Helix gaudryi*, another name has to be applied to the species from Gran Canaria. The oldest available name for the species is *Helix ripochi* J. Mabille, 1882, which is herewith used in the new combination *Hemicycla ripochi* (J. Mabille, 1882). Taking into account locality data as well as conchological characteristics, the synonyms of *gaudryi* sensu auctt (non d’Orbigny) as previously suggested by Bank et al. (2002), i.e., *Helix amblasmodon*, *H. janthina*, *H. themera* and *H. zorgia*, are here considered junior synonyms of *H. ripochi*.

Recent images of a shell are given by C. & N. Evanno on Flickr (Fig. 9) and an image of a living specimen is provided by Frank Walther (Fig. 11). The distribution is summarized by Neiber & Groh, 2025 (Fig. 10).

Hemicycla psathyra (R. T. Lowe, 1861)

Helix (Mycena) psathyra R. T. Lowe, 1861: 109. Type locality: “Hab. in Canaria Magna australiore, praesertim ad Mogan et Aldea de San Nicolas sub saxis in locis aridis apricis”.

Helix (Mycena) psathyra — Oliver, Groh & Ismail, 2024: 22, pl. 8 fig. 95 (page 32).

This species is thought to be widely distributed in the western and southern part of Gran Canaria and is currently divided into three subspecies: *Hemicycla psathyra psathyra*, *H. p. temperata* (Mousson, 1872) and *H. p. bituminosa* (J. Mabille, 1883). Bank et al. (2002: 133) considered *H. ledrui*, described by Mabille, as a synonym of *Helix gaudryi*. However, these authors did not study the type material. Investigation of the type material of *H. ledrui*, preserved in the collection of the MNHN, suggest that this nominal taxon should be regarded as a synonym of *Hemicycla psathyra bituminosa*.

Hemicycla psathyra bituminosa (J. Mabille, 1883)

(Figs 21 to 25)

Helix bituminosa J. Mabille, 1883a: 50-51. Type locality: «La Grande Canarie près de Galder» (ex coll. Ripoché) [= Gáldar [ca 28°8'47"N - 15°39'05"W]]. Syntypes MNHN IM-2000-23262/6 (Figs 23, 23A, lectotype herewith designated).

Helix ledrui J. Mabille, 1883a: 44. Type locality: «Grande Canaries, dans les anciennes sépultures» (ex coll. Ripoché) (more exactly: «La Grande-Canarie fossile dans les tumulus, aux environs d’Agaète» – see Mabille, 1885a: 240. Holotype MNHN IM-2000-29081/1 (Figs. 21, 21A). **Syn. nov.**

Helix bituminosa — Mabille, 1885a: pl. 17 fig. 14 (here reproduced Fig. 24); 1885b: 27-28.

Helix ledrui — Mabille, 1885a: 239-240, pl. 18 fig. 15 (here reproduced Fig. 22).

It should be stressed that the names *H. ledrui* and *H. bituminosa* were introduced in the same paper. As First Revisers (ICZN 1999 Article 24.2.2) we assign precedence to the name *bituminosa*, as this name is currently in use for a subspecies of *Hemicycla psathyra*, whereas *ledrui* has previously been considered one of the synonyms of *Hemicycla gaudryi*. Note that *ledrui* was published a few pages before *bituminosa* in the same publication, but there exists no such thing as “page priority” in the ICZN 1999 Code. To illustrate the variability of the subspecies, we here also include photographs of a shell from the Allspira website (Fig. 25) (<https://allspira.com/product/hemicycla-gaudryi-2/>; photograph C. Dorado).

Preliminary molecular genetic investigations (M.T. Neiber, unpublished data) suggest that *H. ripochi*, as understood here, is closely related to *Hemicycla guamartemes* (Grasset, 1857), *Hemicycla saulcyi* (A. d’Orbigny, 1839) and *Hemicycla ethelema* (J. Mabille, 1882). The *Hemicycla*

Figs 21-25. *Hemicycla psathyra bituminosa* (J. Mabille, 1883). **21.** *Helix ledru* J. Mabille, 1883, holotype MNHN IM-2000-29081, width 26.1 mm (photograph Priscillia Gaël Bourguignon, MNHN). **21a.** Protoconch, magnification from Fig. 21. **22.** *Helix ledru* J. Mabille, 1883, fig. reproduced from Mabille (1885: pl. 18, fig. 15), type locality: “Grande Canarie, environs de Agaète”, Quaternary fossil [ca 28°6'01"N - 15°41'59"W]. **23.** *Helix bituminosa* J. Mabille, 1883, lectotype (here designated) MNHN IM-2000-23262, width 24.2 mm (photograph Priscillia Gaël Bourguignon, MNHN). **23a.** Protoconch, magnification from Fig. 23. **24.** *Helix bituminosa* J. Mabille, 1883, fig. reproduced from Mabille (1885: pl. 17, fig. 14). Type locality: “Grande Canarie, près de Galder”. **25.** *Hemicycla psathyra bituminosa* (J. Mabille, 1883), Gran Canaria, Artenara, from the website of Allspira (<https://allspira.com/search-ngg-images>), width 23.6 mm (photograph Carles Dorado). Scale bar: 5 mm (Figs 21, 23 and 25); Figs 22 and 24 not scaled.

psathyra (R. T. Lowe, 1861) complex, including the currently accepted subspecies *Hemicycla psathyra* s. str., *Hemicycla psathyra temperata* (Mousson, 1872) and *Hemicycla psathyra bituminosa* (J. Mabille, 1883) are in need of further revision. Unpublished molecular genetic data (M.T. Neiber) suggest however that this complex is not closely related to *H. ripochi*.

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